

Realtime Hierarchies using ABAP CDS Views

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Abstract

SAP S/4 HANA offers many advanced capabilities over its previous system versions, one of these is Embedded Analytics. The tools like ABAP CDS views, SET hierarchies and real time hierarchy replication i.e., HRRP_REP help to enable real time operational reporting. For Financial Accounting Business users who work to produce the Quarterly financial results of an organization, having the ability to report on real time data is a key requirement. SET based hierarchies with realtime replication tools help Financial reporting achieve quick turnaround and easy maintenance.

Keywords: SAP S/4 HANA, Embedded Analytics, Operational Reporting, ABAP CDS Views, SET Hierarchies, CDS based virtual hierarchies, HRRP.

1 Introduction: The main purpose of a hierarchy in analytics is to aggregate facts and provide a high-level overview with the option to drill into the lower hierarchy branches and nodes. Facts are represented as CDS analytical views, which are identified by the analytical data category CUBE provided as CDS view annotation. Custom SET Hierarchies can be maintained using transactions GS01/02/03, while the standard dimensions like cost center, profit center and G/L Account hierarchies are maintained using KSH1/2/3, KCH1/2/3, and OB58 respectively. They are replicated using transaction HRRP_REP and stored in database tables HRRP_NODE and HRRP_DIRECTORY. This is then consumed via Hierarchy CDS views to be in turn consumed in the Virtual data model CUBE view.

2 Architecture of Hierarchy CDS views: There are three main types of CDS views for Hierarchies, apart from the text views which can be attached additionally to the Hierarchy views.

- A Dimension CDS view as the master data for the characteristic.
- A Hierarchy Node CDS view to define the hierarchy structure from HRRP_NODE.

- A Hierarchy Directory CDS view to define the available hierarchy names from table HRRP_DIRECTORY.

2.1 Dimension view: This view contains the master data of the characteristic in discussion. Example below is the Cost Center Dimension view which contains the master data for the cost center field from table CSKS. It also has an association to the Hierarchy Node view as well, highlighted in the picture. This is how the hierarchy information is connected with the master data information of the particular dimension.

```
define view I_CostCenter as select distinct from csks
association[1] to I_ControllingArea as _ControllingArea on $projection.ControllingArea = _ControllingArea.ControllingArea
association[0..*] to I_CostCenterText as _Text on $projection.ControllingArea = _Text.ControllingArea and
$projection.CostCenter = _Text.CostCenter
association[0..*] to I_CostCenterHierarchyNode as _CostCenterHierarchyNode on $projection.ControllingArea = _CostCenterHierarchyNode.ControllingArea and
$projection.CostCenter = _CostCenterHierarchyNode.CostCenter
association[0..1] to I_Currency as _Currency on $projection.CostCenterCurrency = _Currency.Currency
association[0..1] to I_CompanyCode as _CompanyCode on $projection.CompanyCode = _CompanyCode.CompanyCode
association[0..1] to I_BusinessArea as _BusinessArea on $projection.BusinessArea = _BusinessArea.BusinessArea
association[0..*] to I_ProfitCenter as _ProfitCenter on $projection.ProfitCenter = _ProfitCenter.ProfitCenter
and $projection.ControllingArea = _ProfitCenter.ControllingArea
association[0..1] to I_FunctionalArea as _FunctionalArea on $projection.FunctionalArea = _FunctionalArea.FunctionalArea
association[0..1] to I_CostCenterCategory as _CostCenterCategory on $projection.CostCenterCategory = _CostCenterCategory.CostCenterCategory
association[0..1] to I_Language as _Language on $projection.Language = _Language.Language

@ObjectModel.foreignKey.association: '_ControllingArea'
//key cast( kokrs as fis_kokrs ) as ControllingArea,
key kokrs as ControllingArea,
@ObjectModel.text.association: '_Text'
@ObjectModel.Hierarchy.association: '_CostCenterHierarchyNode'
key kostl as CostCenter,
```

2.2 Hierarchy Node view: The second view in the set is the Hierarchy Node view. The annotation @ObjectModel.dataCategory: #HIERARCHY specifies the CDS view contains hierarchy nodes. The source of this CDS view is the HRRP_NODE table which stores the information of the nodes in a parent-child relation format. This view has association with the text view of the hierarchy nodes as well to fetch all the text information. The association with the Master data dimension view connects this information with all the possible values of this characteristic available in the master data table. Here is the example of the Hierarchy Node text view which is fetching the text information from the text table of the Node table i.e., HRRP_NODET.

```
6 @EndUserText.label: 'Cost Center Hierarchy Node'
7 @VDM.viewType: #BASIC
8 @AbapCatalog.sqlViewName: 'IFICOSTCENTERHN'
9 @Hierarchy.parentChild:
10 { recurse: { parent: 'ParentNode', child: 'HierarchyNode'
11 siblingsOrder: { by: 'HierarchyNode', direction: 'ASC' },
12 directory: 'Hierarchy'
13 }
14 @AccessControl.authorizationCheck: #NOT_ALLOWED
15 @ClientHandling.algorithm: #SESSION_VARIABLE
16
17 @ObjectModel: {usageType: {
18 dataClass: #MASTER,
19 serviceQuality: #A,
20 sizeCategory: #XL,
21 dataCategory: #HIERARCHY
22 }
23 }
24 define view I_CostCenterHierarchyNode as select from hrrp_node
25
26 association[0..*] to I_CostCenterHierarchyNodeT as _Text
27 on $projection.CostCenterHierarchy = _Text.CostCenterHierarchy
28 and $projection.HierarchyNode = _Text.HierarchyNode
29 and $projection.ControllingArea = _Text.ControllingArea
30 and $projection.CostCenter = '' // just to show that this association is only to be followed if costcenter is blank
31
32 association[0..*] to I_CostCenter as _CostCenter
33 on $projection.CostCenter = _CostCenter.CostCenter
34 and $projection.ControllingArea = _CostCenter.ControllingArea
35
36 association[1..1] to I_CostCenterHierarchy as _Hierarchy
37 on $projection.CostCenterHierarchy = _Hierarchy.CostCenterHierarchy
38 and $projection.ControllingArea = _Hierarchy.ControllingArea
39 and $projection.ValidityEndDate = _Hierarchy.ValidityEndDate
40
41 association[0..1] to I_ControllingArea as _ControllingArea
42 on $projection.ControllingArea = _ControllingArea.ControllingArea
```

2.3 Hierarchy Directory View: The third view in the hierarchy CDS view architecture is the Directory view. This is a Basic view (@VDM.viewType: #BASIC) pulling the information from the table HRRP_DIRECTORY. This provides information about all the hierarchies defined for the Cost Center

dimension. A user can select between the hierarchies to be displayed in the report. This view also has a text view associated with it which is pulling the information from the text table as below.

```

@ObjectModel.representativeKey: 'CostCenterHierarchy' //Inserted by VDM CBS Suite Plugin
@EndUserText.label: 'Cost Center Hierarchy'
@Analytics: { dataCategory: #DIMENSION }
@VDM.viewType: #BASIC
@AbapCatalog.sqlViewName: 'IFICostCenterH'
@AccessControl.authorizationCheck: #CHECK

@ClientHandling.algorithm: #SESSION_VARIABLE
@ObjectModel.usageType: {
  dataClass: #MASTER,
  serviceQuality: #A,
  sizeCategory: #XL
}

define view I_CostCenterHierarchy
  as select from hrrp_directory

  association [1..*] to I_CostCenterHierarchyText as _Text
    on $projection.CostCenterHierarchy = _Text.CostCenterHierarchy
    and $projection.ControllingArea = _Text.ControllingArea

  association [0..1] to I_ControllingArea
    as _ControllingArea on $projection.ControllingArea = _ControllingArea.ControllingArea

{
  @ObjectModel.foreignKey.association: '_ControllingArea'
  key cast( substring( hrrp_directory.hryid, 6, 4) as fis_kokrs ) as ControllingArea,
  @ObjectModel.text.association: '_Text'
  key cast(hrrp_directory.hryid as fis_hryid_cotr) as CostCenterHierarchy,
  @Semantics.businessDate.to: true
  key cast(hrrp_directory.hryvalto as fis_datbi) as ValidityEndDate,
  @Semantics.businessDate.from: true
  cast(hrrp_directory.hryvalfrom as fis_datab) as ValidityStartDate,
  @Semantics.user.lastChangedBy: true
  hrrp_directory.upduser as LastChangedByUser,
  @Semantics.systemDate.lastChangedAt: true
  hrrp_directory.updtime as LastChangeTime,
  _Text,
  _ControllingArea
}

```

```

@EndUserText.label: 'Cost Center Hierarchy Text'
@ObjectModel.representativeKey: 'CostCenterHierarchy'
@Analytics: { dataExtraction.enabled: true }
@ObjectModel.dataCategory: #TEXT
@VDM.viewType: #BASIC
@AbapCatalog.sqlViewName: 'IFICOSTCENTERHT'
@AccessControl.authorizationCheck: #NOT_REQUIRED

@ClientHandling.algorithm: #SESSION_VARIABLE
@ObjectModel.usageType: {
  dataClass: #MASTER,
  serviceQuality: #A,
  sizeCategory: #XL
}

define view I_CostCenterHierarchyText as select from hrrp_directoryt

  association [0..1] to I_ControllingArea as _ControllingArea
    on $projection.ControllingArea = _ControllingArea.ControllingArea

  association [0..1] to I_Language as _Language
    on $projection.Language = _Language.Language

{
  @ObjectModel.foreignKey.association: '_ControllingArea'
  key substring( hrrp_directoryt.hryid, 6, 4) as ControllingArea,
  key hrrp_directoryt.hryid as CostCenterHierarchy,
  @Semantics.businessDate.to: true
  key hrrp_directoryt.hryvalto as ValidityEndDate,
  @Semantics.language
  key spras as Language,
  @Semantics.businessDate.from: true
  hrrp_directoryt.hryvalfrom as ValidityStartDate,
  @Semantics.text
  hrytxt as CostCenterHierarchyName,
  _ControllingArea,
  _Language
};

```

Now that we have seen the architecture of the CDS views involved in the virtual Data Model, let us take a look at the other key aspect of the Hierarchies, which is replication.

3 Replication of Hierarchy Information: Replication of the hierarchy is also referred to as the activation. A hierarchy can only be used in the reporting tools after it is replicated. This also allows developers to have an option of changes in the hierarchy to be made available at a later point in time by scheduling the

replication. There are two main tables which store the hierarchy information once it is replicated, namely **HRRP_DIRECTORY** and **HRRP_NODE**. **HRRP_DIRECTORY** table stores the information whenever a hierarchy is replicated with hierarchy name, replication date and user information. This table is the source of Information of the Directory CDS view seen in the section 2.3 above. If a new hierarchy is created on the same characteristic, a new entry is created in the **HRRP_DIRECTORY** table. **HRRP_NODE** table stores the information of the hierarchy nodes and their parent child relationship. This is the source table for the Hierarchy Node CDS view seen in the section 2.2 above. Both of these tables have their respective text tables namely, **HRRP_DIRECTORYT** and **HRRP_NODET** which are used in the respective text CDS views as a source. Transaction code **HRRP_REP** is used to replicate a hierarchy. You need to enter the hierarchy ID in the field and then execute the transaction code. Once executed, the hierarchy information is stored in the **HRRP*** tables discussed above which are then in turn ready to be used in the reports. As you can see in the picture below, this transaction code also provides options such as deletion of the hierarchy replication, in case you would like to stop using a hierarchy. Scheduling option helps to schedule the changes in the hierarchy at a later point in time. Prerequisite- the transaction code **HRY_REPRELEV** is used to make a hierarchy "report relevant" before replicating it in the transaction code **HRRP_REP**.

Manually Replicate Runtime Hierarchy (New) (With Job Scheduler)

Hierarchy Creation

Hierarchy ID [] []

Hierarchy Deletion

Hierarchy ID []

By Date

Version Older than []

By Version

Hierarchy Version [] 0 to [] 0 []

Run Settings

Run Now in Foreground

Run Now in Background

Run Periodically in Background

Periodic Settings

Start On []

Start At [00:00:00]

End On []

End At [00:00:00]

Frequency

Daily

Weekly

Monthly

Similar to the example of Cost Center CDS views, custom views can be created for any custom Characteristic in the report. Once Hierarchy CDS views are created and replicated, they are ready to be used in the Report by attaching them using the association to the CUBE CDS view of the data model. Below

example shows the CUBE view(Analytics.dataCategory:#CUBE) of the Joint venture Accounting Details, which has the Cost Center Dimension view being used as an Association. This association also needs to be attached to the cost center field using an annotation.

```

1 @ObjectModel.foreignKey.association: '_CostCenter'
2 rcntr as CostCenter.
3
4
5
6
7
8 @ClientHandling.algorithm: #SESSION_VARIABLE
9 @ObjectModel.usageType.sizeCategory: #XL
10 @ObjectModel.usageType.serviceQuality: #D
11 @ObjectModel.usageType.dataClass: #MIXED
12
13 define view I_JointVentureAccogDetail
14 as select from yvaol
15 association [0..1] to I_Ledger as _Ledger on $Projection.Ledger = _Ledger.Ledger
16 association [0..1] to I_JVARecordType as _RecordType on $Projection.RecordType = _RecordType.JVARecordType
17 association [0..1] to I_DebitCreditCode as _DebitCreditCode on $Projection.DebitCreditCode = _DebitCreditCode.DebitCreditCode
18 association [0..1] to I_SpecialLedgerVersion as _SpecialLedgerVersion on $Projection.Ledger = _SpecialLedgerVersion.Ledger
19 and $Projection.SpecialLedgerVersion = _SpecialLedgerVersion.SpecialLedgerVersion
20 association [0..1] to I_Currency as _Currency on $Projection.Currency = _Currency.Currency
21 association [0..1] to I_UnitOfMeasure as _UnitOfMeasure on $Projection.UnitOfMeasure = _UnitOfMeasure.UnitOfMeasure
22 association [0..1] to I_CompanyCode as _CompanyCode on $Projection.CompanyCode = _CompanyCode.CompanyCode
23 association [0..1] to I_JVADocumentType as _DocumentType on $Projection.DocumentType = _DocumentType.JVADocumentType
24
25 association [0..1] to I_JointVenture as _JointVenture on $Projection.CompanyCode = _JointVenture.CompanyCode
26 and $Projection.JointVenture = _JointVenture.JointVenture
27 association [0..1] to I_JointVentureEquityGroup as _JointVentureEquityGroup on $Projection.CompanyCode = _JointVentureEquityGroup.CompanyCode
28 and $Projection.JointVenture = _JointVentureEquityGroup.JointVenture
29 and $Projection.JointVentureEquityGroup = _JointVentureEquityGroup.JointVentureEquityGroup
30 association [0..1] to I_ChartOfAccounts as _ChartOfAccounts on $Projection.ChartOfAccounts = _ChartOfAccounts.ChartOfAccounts
31 association [0..1] to I_GLAccount as _GLAccount on $Projection.CompanyCode = _GLAccount.CompanyCode
32 and $Projection.GLAccount = _GLAccount.GLAccount
33 association [0..1] to I_GLAccountInChartOfAccounts as _GLAccountInChartOfAccounts on $Projection.ChartOfAccounts = _GLAccountInChartOfAccounts.ChartOfAccounts
34 and $Projection.GLAccount = _GLAccountInChartOfAccounts.GLAccount
35 association [0..1] to I_BusinessArea as _BusinessArea on $Projection.BusinessArea = _BusinessArea.BusinessArea
36 association [0..1] to I_ControllingArea as _ControllingArea on $Projection.ControllingArea = _ControllingArea.ControllingArea
37 association [0..*] to I_CostCenter as _CostCenter on $Projection.ControllingArea = _CostCenter.ControllingArea
38 and $Projection.CostCenter = CostCenter.CostCenter

```

Conclusion:

In SAP S/4HANA Embedded Analytics CDS-based Hierarchy Views and the HRRP_REP transaction code are instrumental in establishing and managing reporting hierarchies for operational reporting. ABAP CDS views allow the definition of hierarchical structures directly within the data model that reporting tools can readily consume. The HRRP_REP transaction, known as the FIN Runtime Hierarchy Replicator, is used to replicate runtime hierarchies within the SAP system. This approach enables hierarchies in the reporting tools without any inconsistency as the information is pulled straight from the source and the transaction code allows the deletion and scheduling features which help maintain the hierarchies effectively.

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